

APRIMORANDO A APRENDIZAGEM NO LABORATÓRIO DE QUÍMICA: EFEITO DE SIMULAÇÕES PRÉ-LABORATORIAIS E DE FLUXOGRAMAS NO DESEMPENHO DE FUTUROS PROFESSORES

ENHANCING LEARNING IN CHEMISTRY LABORATORY: EFFECT OF PRE-LAB SIMULATIONS AND FLOWCHART ON PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS' ACHIEVEMENT

KİMYA LABORATUVARINDA ÖĞRENMENİN GELİŞTİRİLMESİ: SİMÜLASYON VE AKIŞ ŞEMASININ ÖĞRETMEN ADAYLARININ BAŞARISINA ETKİSİ

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RESUMO

Introdução: Simulações são amplamente utilizadas na educação para proporcionar ambientes de aprendizagem dinâmicos e são particularmente úteis na química, onde podem substituir experimentos físicos quando as condições de laboratório são inadequadas ou os materiais forem perigosos. Neste estudo, as simulações foram empregadas não como substitutas, mas para potencializar a eficácia dos experimentos laboratoriais presenciais. **Objetivo:** O estudo teve como objetivo investigar o impacto do uso de simulações e fluxogramas na instrução sobre preparo de soluções e aquecimento sobre o desempenho acadêmico de futuros professores de química, além de explorar suas opiniões sobre a preparação para experimentos práticos por meio de simulações pré-laboratoriais. **Métodos:** Adotou-se um delineamento do tipo grupo estático com pré-teste e pós-teste, envolvendo 21 futuros professores matriculados na disciplina de Laboratório de Química Geral. A instrução ocorreu em duas etapas: primeiro, os experimentos foram realizados online por meio de simulações; em seguida, os mesmos experimentos foram executados em laboratório físico. Os dados foram coletados por meio de quizzes (pré-teste), uma prova de desempenho (pós-teste) e um formulário de feedback. **Resultados:** O teste de Wilcoxon indicou que os experimentos laboratoriais apoiados por simulações tiveram um efeito positivo e estatisticamente significativo no desempenho dos participantes. Além disso, o teste de Mann-Whitney U revelou diferença significativa entre as notas do pós-teste dos futuros professores que elaboraram um fluxograma com base nas simulações e aqueles que não o fizeram. **Discussão:** O uso de simulações para enriquecer experimentos laboratoriais proporciona uma experiência de aprendizagem mais rica e diversificada, combinando vivências concretas e virtuais. Os fluxogramas elaborados pelos participantes não eram meras listas de procedimentos, mas incluíam também propriedades das substâncias utilizadas, pontos-chave a serem observados e lembretes importantes. Essa prática favoreceu uma aprendizagem duradoura ao desenvolver habilidades de organização, associação e aplicação do conhecimento. **Conclusões:** Concluiu-se que a realização de simulações antes dos experimentos laboratoriais melhora significativamente o desempenho acadêmico. Ademais, os futuros professores que tanto realizaram as simulações quanto elaboraram fluxogramas obtiveram pontuações superiores às de seus colegas. Os participantes também relataram menor ansiedade, maior confiança e consideraram as simulações benéficas para o planejamento e a execução dos experimentos.

Palavras-chave: Simulações, fluxogramas, laboratório de química, desempenho, futuros professores.

ABSTRACT

Background: Simulations are widely used in education to provide dynamic learning environments and are particularly useful in chemistry, where they can substitute for physical experiments when laboratory conditions are inadequate or materials hazardous. In this study, simulations were employed not as replacements but to enhance the effectiveness of physical laboratory experiments. **Aim:** The study aimed to investigate the impact of simulation- and flowchart-supported instruction on solution preparation and heating on the academic achievement

of pre-service chemistry teachers, and to explore their opinions about preparing for hands-on experiments by first conducting a pre-lab simulation. **Methods:** The study employed a static group pretest-posttest design, involving 21 pre-service teachers enrolled in the General Chemistry Laboratory course. Instruction proceeded in two stages: first, experiments were conducted online through simulations; second, the same experiments were performed in a physical laboratory. Data were collected via quizzes (pretest), an achievement exam (posttest), and a feedback form. **Results:** The Wilcoxon Signed Rank test indicated that simulation-supported laboratory experiments had a significant positive effect on participants' achievement. Additionally, the Mann–Whitney U test revealed a significant difference between the posttest scores of pre-service teachers who prepared a flowchart using simulations and those who did not. **Discussion:** Enhancing laboratory experiments with simulations provides a richer and more varied learning experience by offering both concrete and virtual experiences. Flowcharts drawn up by the participants were not simple lists of steps, but also covered the properties of the chemicals utilized, key points to consider, and significant reminders. This supported durable learning through enhancing students' skills in organizing, associating, and applying knowledge. **Conclusions:** In conclusion, running simulations before laboratory experiments has been shown to improve academic achievement. Moreover, pre-service teachers who both conducted the simulations and prepared their flowcharts achieved higher scores than their peers. Participants also reported reduced anxiety, increased confidence, and perceived simulations as beneficial for planning and carrying out the experiments.

Keywords: *Simulations, flowcharts, chemistry laboratory, achievement, pre-service teachers*

ÖZET

Giriş: Simülasyonlar, eğitimde dinamik öğrenme ortamları yaratmak için yaygın olarak kullanılmakta ve özellikle kimya alanında, laboratuvar koşullarının yetersiz olduğu ya da materyallerin tehlikeli olduğu durumlarda fiziksel deneylerin yerine geçebilmektedir. Bu çalışmada ise simülasyonlar, fiziksel laboratuvar deneylerinin etkinliğini artırmak amacıyla kullanılmıştır. **Amaç:** Araştırma, çözelti hazırlama ve ısıtma konularında simülasyon ve akış şeması destekli öğretimin öğretmen adaylarının akademik başarıları üzerindeki etkisini incelemeyi ve deney öncesinde simülasyon yaparak uygulamaya hazırlanma sürecine ilişkin görüşlerini belirlemeyi amaçlamaktadır. **Yöntem:** Statik grup ön test-son test desen kullanılan çalışmaya, Genel Kimya Laboratuvarı dersine kayıtlı 21 öğretmen adayı katılmıştır. Süreç iki aşamada yürütülmüştür: (1) çevrimiçi simülasyon uygulamaları, (2) aynı deneylerin fiziksel laboratuvarda gerçekleştirilmesi. Veriler, quizler (ön test), başarı testi (son test) ve geri bildirim formu ile toplanmıştır. **Bulgular:** Wilcoxon testi, simülasyon destekli laboratuvar uygulamalarının ve simülasyon+akış şeması hazırlanarak yapılan uygulamaların öğretmen adaylarının akademik başarılarını anlamlı biçimde artırdığını; Mann–Whitney testi ise simülasyonları tamamladıktan sonra akış şeması hazırlayan öğretmen adaylarının akademik başarılarının daha yüksek olduğunu göstermiştir. **Tartışma:** Simülasyon ve laboratuvar deneylerinin birleşimi öğrencilere hem somut hem sanal deneyimler sunarak daha zengin bir öğrenme süreci sağlamıştır. Katılımcıların hazırladığı akış şemaları yalnızca adımları değil, kimyasalların özelliklerini, dikkat edilmesi gereken noktaları ve önemli hatırlatmaları da içermiştir. Bu süreç, bilgiyi organize etme, ilişkilendirme ve uygulama becerilerini geliştirerek kalıcı öğrenmeyi desteklemiştir. **Sonuç:** Hem laboratuvar deneylerinden önce yapılan simülasyonların hem de simülasyonunun tamamlanmasının ardından hazırlanan bireysel akış şemalarının öğretmen adaylarının akademik başarılarını artırdığı yapılan analizler sonucunda belirlenmiştir. Ancak bu iki uygulama türü kıyaslandığında, simülasyonları tamamladıktan sonra akış şeması hazırlayan ve fiziksel laboratuvardaki deneyleri bu akış şemasına göre hazırlayan öğretmen adaylarının akademik başarılarının sadece simülasyon yapan öğretmen adaylarından daha yüksek olduğu belirlenmiştir. Ayrıca katılımcıların simülasyonları kaygıyı azaltıcı, özgüven artırıcı ve deneyleri kolaylaştırıcı buldukları belirlenmiştir.

Anahtar kelimeler: *Simülasyon, akış şeması, kimya laboratuvarı, başarı, öğretmen adayları*

1. INTRODUCTION:

Chemistry is a branch of science where abstract and concrete ideas interact (Yazıcı, 2023). Concretization of abstract concepts occurs through laboratory activities in chemistry education. In this way, laboratories play an important role in chemistry education. Laboratories, where students gain experience by direct practice or observation, are an important source of information obtained in chemistry, an

experimental science. Practical laboratory experiments provide students with invaluable insights into the principles and practices of the discipline (Ayas, Akdeniz & Çepni, 1994).

Additionally, experimental learning increases students' interest in the subject and makes learning more enjoyable and permanent (Aydoğdu & Erbaş, 1992; Yao, 2023). Several methods/strategies that support physical laboratory environments are employed to enhance students' chemistry achievements. Encouraging

students' active participation in laboratory studies, such as through group work, and ensuring their involvement in discussion and experiment design processes can make laboratory experiences more effective. These interventions, along with the use of laboratory-supporting technology, can help students better understand chemistry concepts (Hofstein & Lunetta, 2004; Nakhleh, 1992; Russell & Weaver, 2011).

Nowadays, just as laboratories are important in chemistry education, technology is also crucial in education, and its importance is increasing daily. While the student's learning is supported through concrete experiences, supplementing it with visual experiences provides a rich teaching process. One of the environments that provides visual experience in this way is virtual learning environments (Ergun, 2017). Simulations, which enable students to gain experience, model real-life scenarios through computer-aided technological environments (Dalgarno, 2001; Lee *et al.*, 2021). Through simulations, students can explore and observe the microscopic world of chemistry more flexibly and freely. Simulations provide students with a unique opportunity to visualize abstract concepts and complex chemical phenomena with clarity. Simulations make theoretical concepts concrete and accessible by representing molecular structures, reactions, and interactions in dynamic, three-dimensional environments (Hirst, Glowacki & Baaden, 2014; Rayan & Rayan, 2017). Through simulations, students can explore and observe the microscopic world of chemistry more flexibly and engagingly (Hakerem, Dobrynina & Shore, 1993; Pekdağ, 2009). Unlike physical laboratories, where experiments are often limited by time and resources, simulations offer unlimited opportunities for exploration and experimentation. Students can repeat experiments multiple times, vary the variables, and observe the results immediately, thereby promoting a deeper understanding of chemical principles.

Simulations can help students understand complex concepts and serve as an effective tool in chemistry education. However, experimental simulations also have some limitations. In particular, it remains a matter of debate whether the practical skills acquired in real experiments are equivalent to those gained in simulations (Hawkins & Phelps, 2013). For this reason, the process of this study was structured in such a way that simulations and practical experiments supported each other. In addition, it was aimed to ensure the permanence of the knowledge of the pre-service teachers who investigated the theoretical

knowledge about the experiment by transferring this information to the flowcharts.

Flowcharts are learning tools that aim to prepare pre-service teachers for the concepts and procedures they will encounter in the laboratory (Davidowitz, Rollnick, & Fakudze, 2005). While flowcharts are used to illustrate the experimental strategy and the steps to be followed in a process (Nakiboğlu, Erdurmazlı, Kızmaz, & Hepöz), they also enable students to develop concepts independently. Students' feedback that flowcharts help them associate experiments with chemical concepts covered in the lessons supports this feature of flowcharts (Davidowitz & Rollnick, 2001).

Laboratory practices, a vital part of chemistry education, enable students to connect abstract concepts with real-world experiences and consolidate their knowledge. Yet, when students do not prepare sufficiently for experiments, follow procedures superficially from a guide, and carry out the process without careful consideration, both their academic success and laboratory safety can be compromised. In general chemistry labs, it is commonly seen that students commit conceptual mistakes, waste time, and finish the period without completely fulfilling the purpose of the experiment. At this juncture, pre-laboratory tools such as simulations and self-designed flowcharts can play a crucial role in making the laboratory process more structured and meaningful. Simulations offer students the opportunity to review experimental procedures and minimize the risk of errors. In contrast, flowcharts allow them to chart the procedure in their own language and identify critical points. Thus, an investigation into the role of simulation- and flowchart-assisted practices in laboratory accomplishment is deemed important. The primary objective of this research was to investigate the impact of various pre-laboratory preparation methods on the academic performance of pre-service chemistry teachers in general chemistry laboratory practices. More specifically, the study investigated (i) changes in achievement levels of pre-service teachers who used simulations before conducting laboratory experiments, and (ii) changes in achievement levels of those who, in addition to using simulations, created individual flowcharts prior to performing the experiments. In addition, the research aimed to gain qualitative insights into pre-service teachers' views on using simulation-based experiments as a preparatory step before engaging in hands-on laboratory work, through semi-structured interviews.

1.1. Aim of the study

This research aims to investigate the impact of combining flowchart elaboration tasks with simulation-based laboratory activities on the academic achievement of pre-service teachers. In particular, the research aims to compare the level of achievement of a group of pre-service teachers who only participated in simulations with that of a group of pre-service teachers who, in addition to simulations, designed flowcharts prior to conducting laboratory experiments.

1. Is there a difference in the achievement scores of pre-service teachers in the control group depending on their pretest and posttest results after participating in simulation activities?
2. Is there a difference in the achievement scores of pre-service teachers in the experimental group depending on their pretest and posttest results after participating in simulation and flowchart preparation activities?
3. Is there a difference in the academic achievement of pre-service teachers based on whether they only performed simulations or performed simulations together with flowchart preparation?
4. What are the perceptions of pre-service teachers regarding the use of simulation activities prior to conducting physical laboratory experiments?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW:

Simulations can be used for various purposes in chemistry education, including pre-laboratory preparation, laboratory safety training, visualization of complex concepts, accessibility, and experimental design and analysis (Figure 1). Simulations can help students prepare for laboratory experiments. It allows students to visually follow the progress of the experiment, making it easier for them to understand the purposes of the experiment (Agustian & Seery, 2017; Navarro Arias-Calderón, Henríquez & Riquelme, 2024). Additionally, simulations provide students with practice in laboratory safety, offering knowledge about the use of hazardous chemicals and the correct use of laboratory equipment. Such experiences can significantly enhance overall safety within the laboratory environment (Kong *et al.*, 2022). Simulations can be used to visualize abstract or complex chemistry concepts. For example, simulations can be used to illustrate the dynamics of molecular structures or describe the mechanisms of chemical reactions (Fombana-Pascual, Fombona, & Vicente, 2022; Magaña &

Jong, 2018).

Furthermore, simulations may be useful for students with limited access to physical laboratory facilities. By engaging in simulated environments, these students can replicate the laboratory experience, thus bridging the gap caused by limited access to actual labs (Dunnagan & Gallardo-Williams, 2020). Moreover, simulations provide students with the opportunity to analyze the results of experiments and practice experimental design. Such experiences are instrumental in nurturing students' capacity for scientific reasoning and analytical thinking (Wörner, Kuhn & Scheiter, 2022).

Figure 1. Purposes of using simulations in chemistry education

Despite engaging in laboratory experiments, pre-service chemistry teachers often fail to fully grasp fundamental chemistry concepts and complete their studies with inadequate knowledge of chemistry. There are studies in the literature that investigate the reasons for this lack of knowledge. One of the important reasons that stands out among these is the lack of theoretical context (Çalık & Ayas, 2005; Nakhleh, 1992; Finne, Gammelgaard & Christiansen, 2022). Suppose students fail to establish connections between theoretical knowledge and their execution of laboratory experiments. In that case, they risk obtaining inaccurate results and engaging in ineffective practices. Understanding the relationship between experimental results and theoretical concepts might pose a challenge for them (Finne, Gammelgaard & Christiansen, 2023; Talanquer & Pollard, 2010; Tümay, 2016). The combination of simulations and experiments in a

physical laboratory environment can provide students with a richer learning experience. This approach diversifies the learning process by offering students both concrete and virtual experiences. Additionally, it offers instructors increased flexibility in curriculum design and the choice of experiments tailored to meet the needs of students. Employing this integrated method can enhance students' ability to think scientifically and develop a more profound comprehension of chemistry subjects (Hofstein & Lunetta, 2004; Nakhleh, 1992).

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

3.1. Research Design and Participants

A static group pretest-posttest design was used in the research. The static group pretest-posttest design uses two naturally formed or pre-existing groups. Since these groups do not change, they are usually described as static groups, hence the name of the design (Fraenkel, Wallen & Hyun, 2012). This research design is characterized by a linear sequence (i.e., pretest-posttest design) that requires the dependent variable to be assessed before and after administration. In pretest-posttest research designs, the effect of the application is determined by comparing the difference between the initial assessment and the final assessment. Before starting the research, a pretest is administered to the participants. The practitioner then implements the teaching method whose effectiveness will be examined, followed by a posttest. Then, the change in pretest and posttest scores is examined (Mertler, 2022).

A purposeful sampling method was employed to select the research sample. Purposeful sampling is the process of selecting a sample by taking into account the prior knowledge of a group based on the purpose of the research to be conducted (Fraenkel *et al.*, 2012). The biggest advantage of this method is that it provides the opportunity to easily reach the sample group (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2013). The sample group of the study consists of 21 volunteer pre-service chemistry teachers taking the General Chemistry Laboratory course I at the Education Faculty of a state university in Türkiye. The research was carried out in the General Chemistry Laboratory course.

3.2. Data Collection Tools

Open-ended question form (Quiz and achievement exam): The research data were

collected through quizzes administered before the physical laboratory experiments (hands-on experiments) and an achievement exam after the implementation was completed. The quiz and achievement exam are parallel exam versions containing similar questions. The grade point average of the two quizzes was evaluated as a pretest. The achievement exam was evaluated as a posttest. The questions asked in the quiz and achievement exam were taken as written answers, with two open-ended questions that included calculations, problem-solving, and explanations. In the first question, a question was asked about solutions, which is the first subject of the general chemistry laboratory. Here, the points to be considered during solution preparation and heating processes should be noted. In the second question, it is expected to prepare a solution from a solid substance, solve the problem, and identify the steps involved in preparing the solution. The pre-service teachers were given 25 minutes to answer the questions in the quizzes and achievement exam. Throughout the research process, a total of two quizzes were administered, each prior to an experiment, and an achievement exam was given as a posttest at the end of the study. Prior the main study, a pilot study was conducted to examine the clarity, validity, and reliability of the quizzes and achievement exam. Necessary revisions were made based on feedback from pre-service teachers, and expert opinions were also considered to ensure the suitability of the instruments.

Feedback form: To conduct an in-depth examination of pre-service teachers' perspectives on the simulation activity, researchers developed a semi-structured interview form consisting of seven open-ended questions. The form contained questions such as: "What are your opinions about the simulation activities? When performing experiments in the laboratory, to what extent and in what ways do the simulations influence your performance? What recommendations would you make to enhance the effectiveness of simulation activities conducted in conjunction with laboratory work?" For the form, the opinions of two experts, one from the Chemistry Education Department and the other from the Educational Sciences Department, were consulted. The pre-service teachers were given 45 minutes to complete the form. The feedback form was only applied once, after the research process was completed.

3.3. Research Procedure

During the research process, two simulations and two physical experiments on the subject of "Preparation of Solutions and Heating of

Solutions" were carried out by the pre-service teachers. Before implementation, they were divided into five groups, each consisting of 3-4 people. The research process consists of two consecutive steps. In the first step, the experiments were conducted online through a simulation application as out-of-class activities, and experiment flowcharts were prepared based on the simulations created by pre-service teachers. In the second step, all pre-service teachers conducted experiments using real materials and equipment in a physical laboratory environment. Simulation instructions and experiment sheets were e-mailed to all pre-service teachers before the physical laboratory experiments. The experiment sheet includes theoretical information and experiment materials, while the simulation instruction contains a link to the simulation's web page and questions for pre-service teachers to discuss and answer while performing the simulation. After completing the simulation, a quiz was administered to the pre-service teachers in the physical laboratory environment, and then each experiment was conducted. Four weeks after the simulations and experiments were completed, achievement exams and feedback forms were administered to the pre-service teachers. The achievement exam was administered as a posttest, and the feedback form was administered once after the entire research process was completed. The research process is summarized in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Implementation process of the research

For online simulations, a web 2.0 tool called Online Labs (OLabs) was used. OLabs is a web-based learning environment for science practical experiments, featuring simulations, animations, tutorials, and assessments. The groups performed the simulations online on the Microsoft Teams platform. The stages of performing the simulation were recorded by the pre-service teachers so that the researchers could follow the process. While the simulation was being carried out, pre-service teachers were asked to answer the questions in the simulation instruction

and to complete the simulation after solving the questions that arose during the process by discussing them with their peers. Each pre-service teacher was required to create an individual experimental flowchart after completing the simulations. They were advised to utilize the simulation during the process of building the flowchart and to incorporate tips that would guide them during the experiment, based on their own investigation. During the implementation process, however, only 11 pre-service teachers actually prepared a flowchart in conjunction with the simulations. Consequently, these 11 pre-service teachers conducted the experiments in the laboratory using their own flowcharts. In contrast, the other 10 pre-service teachers conducted the experiments with the help of experiment sheets designed by the researchers, which contained the experimental procedures. Due to this circumstance, the study compared the levels of achievement of two different groups: participants who only experienced the simulation and the laboratory experiment, and those who, after the simulation, created a flowchart prior to performing the laboratory experiment.

3.4. Data Analysis

Analysis of quantitative data. Quantitative data obtained from the study were analyzed using SPSS version 23. The assumption of normality was examined using the Shapiro-Wilk test prior to analysis. Since the results indicated a violation of normality ($p < .05$), and based on the advice from the literature to use non-parametric tests when the sample size is below 30 (Fraenkel et al., 2012), non-parametric approaches were employed. To test the change in each group, the Wilcoxon Signed Rank test was used to make pretest-posttest comparisons of achievement scores. The Mann-Whitney U test was also used to determine if the posttest scores of the control group (simulation only) differed significantly from those of the experimental group (simulation and flowchart). This provided the basis for testing both within-group and between-group achievement differences.

Analysis of qualitative data. Qualitative data of the research were collected through a feedback form. The data obtained was analyzed by content analysis. Content analysis enables individuals to identify indicators of worldviews, values, attitudes, biases, and opinions, and compare them across communities (Bauer, 2000). Analysis of qualitative data obtained from interviews. It was carried out by following the steps of coding the data (1), creating themes (2), organizing the codes and themes (3), determining and interpreting the findings (4) (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2013).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

4.1. Results

4.1.1 Quantitative findings

In this study, while only the simulation activity was carried out in the control group, the experimental group also included an additional flowchart preparation activity alongside the simulation. The Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test was used to examine the difference between the groups' pretest and posttest achievement scores. The findings are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

As shown in Table 1, there is a statistically significant difference between the pretest and posttest achievement scores of the pre-service teachers in the control group ($Z = -2.312$, $p = .021$). From this finding, it can be stated that laboratory experiments assisted by simulation enhance students' success through conceptual preparation prior to the experiment.

As shown in Table 2, there is a statistically significant difference between the pretest and posttest achievement scores of the pre-service teachers in the experimental group ($Z = -2.807$, $p = .005$). This finding indicates that, in addition to the simulation activity, the flowchart preparation activity provided an extra contribution to achievement.

The pretest–posttest analyses conducted for both groups showed that both the simulation activity and the simulation combined with the flowchart preparation activity increased the achievement of pre-service teachers. However, determining which approach was more effective required a comparison of the applications. Therefore, whether there was a significant difference between the two groups' posttest achievement scores was examined using the Mann-Whitney U test. Group A represents the control group, which only carried out the simulation activity. In contrast, Group B represents the experimental group, which carried out both the simulation and the preparation of the flowchart. The findings are presented in Table 3.

As shown in Table 3, there is a statistically significant difference between the experimental and control groups in terms of posttest achievement scores ($U = 15.000$, $Z = -2.822$, $p = .005$). It was determined that the achievement of the pre-service teachers who prepared a flowchart in addition to the simulation activity was higher. This situation reveals that chemistry laboratory experiments, supported by simulation and flowcharts, have a positive effect on academic

achievement. On the one hand, they enhance academic achievement, and on the other hand, they provide a deeper understanding of the subject and direct students to preliminary preparation and study.

4.1.2 Qualitative findings

Content analysis was conducted in four steps: coding the data, identifying themes, organizing the data according to themes and codes, and interpreting the findings. The data obtained from the feedback form was collected under two themes. As seen in Table 4, these themes are cognitive contribution and affective contribution.

Table 4. Themes and codes of qualitative analysis feedback form

Themes	Code
Cognitive contribution	Transfer of knowledge Organization of prior knowledge
Affective contribution	Feel ready to experiment Confidence Anxiety

According to the analysis of the interviews, two themes emerged. These are cognitive contribution and affective contribution. Two codes describe the first theme, cognitive contribution. These codes are "transfer of knowledge" and "organization of prior knowledge". The expressions for the knowledge transfer code are as follows: "*I understood what kind of relationship there is between chemistry and technology [PST7], I have now realized that if I do not adjust the volume correctly while preparing the solution, there will not be a solution at the desired concentration [PST18]*". In the code of organizing preliminary learning, "*The simulations before the experiment helped me understand what the solution preparation was [PST14], I realized that I misunderstood the concentration and concentration units of the solution [PST20]*".

The second theme from the feedback form analysis is affective contribution. The codes of the affective contribution themes are 'feel ready to experiment', 'confidence', and 'anxiety'. The expressions for feeling ready to experiment with code are as follows. "*Since I had never done any experiments in high school, simulation prepared me for experimenting in the laboratory [PST3], to experiment, there are first calculation, then material preparation, and then experiment steps [PST17]*". The statements in the confidence code are as follows: "*I ran the experiment multiple times in the simulation, which helped me prepare well for the lab [PST21], I wrote*

down the steps I followed in the simulation and created a flowchart for myself, using this in the lab prevented me from making mistakes [PST2]". In the code of anxiety, "Just preparing for the experiment with the leaflet worried me, I'm glad I did a practice with the simulation beforehand [PST8], I feel like I can do all the experiments by preparing in advance with simulation, I no longer have any fear of the laboratory [PST19]".

4.2. Discussion

This study aimed to investigate the effects of simulations used prior to laboratory experiments and student-oriented flowcharts prepared by pre-service teachers on their academic achievement and overall learning experiences in general chemistry laboratory implementations. The results of the study indicate that simulation activities performed before the laboratory significantly enhanced the academic achievement of pre-service teachers. This suggests that simulations help pre-service teachers mentally prepare for experimental processes (Salame & Makki, 2021). Similarly, previous studies have shown that simulations support conceptual learning, reduce errors, increase self-confidence, and provide more active participation in the learning process (Rutten, van Joolingen & van der Veen, 2012; Tatlı & Ayas, 2013).

In this simulation-supported process, the pre-service teachers had the opportunity to see the experimental steps in advance and were involved in an active learning environment through in-group discussions, which allowed them to think critically about these steps. Especially in complex chemistry experiments involving abstract concepts, simulations are very useful in structuring the experiment in the mind before it begins (Orgill & Thomas, 2007; Rayan & Rayan, 2017). The combination of laboratory experiments and simulations can provide students with a richer learning experience. This approach diversifies the learning process by providing students with both concrete experiences and virtual experiences. The combined approach can help students develop scientific thinking skills and a deeper understanding of chemistry topics. These skills are often not sufficiently developed in students who only work with an experiment sheet (Hofstein & Lunetta, 2004). In this context, simulation-supported learning is thought to contribute to achievement, especially at the implementation level, as measured by open-ended questions.

Another prominent finding of the study is that pre-service teachers who prepared flowcharts about the experiment after the simulation showed higher success compared to those who did not prepare these diagrams. This shows that pre-

service teachers' structuring the steps of the experiment in their own words deepened their cognitive processes and enabled them to act more consciously during the experiment. According to Domin (1999), flowcharts are a tool that enables students to interpret experiments more effectively than traditional experiment sheets. He emphasized that in experiments with traditional experiment sheets, students only focus on completing the task and try to fulfill the instructions. In addition, providing students with an experiment sheet that outlines the steps of the experiment does not guarantee that they have studied this guide before coming to the laboratory. However, it is advantageous for students to prepare their own flowcharts to make sense of the experimental steps, recognize the materials/chemicals to be used in the experiment, and interpret the results (Davidowitz et al., 2005). The flowcharts prepared were not only a listing of the experiment's steps, but also included the properties of the chemicals used, key considerations, and important reminders. This process supports the realization of permanent learning by improving students' ability to organize, associate, and apply knowledge. This finding can be explained by generative learning theory (Wittrock, 1989). According to this theory, learning becomes more permanent when students actively reconstruct knowledge. The process of preparing a flowchart enabled students to internalize the experimental steps and to critically evaluate the rationale behind each step. Studies in the literature also emphasize that student-centered tools, such as flowcharts, contribute to long-term learning and enable students to act more independently in the experimental process (Eilks & Byers, 2010).

Qualitative data analysis revealed that pre-service teachers thought that simulation-supported laboratory practices contributed to both cognitive and affective aspects. As cognitive contributions, pre-service teachers stated that the simulations helped them organize their prior knowledge, and they were able to remember and transfer what they learned in the laboratory more easily. These findings support constructivist learning approaches, which are based on active participation and the activation of prior knowledge (Ausubel, 1968; National Research Council, 2000). They stated that, thanks to the simulations, they were able to concentrate their attention better and comprehend the logic of the experiment more clearly because they had seen the processes they would encounter in the experiment beforehand. In terms of affective contribution, it was observed that simulations reduced pre-service teachers' anxiety before the experiment, increased their self-

confidence, and helped them feel more prepared for the experiment. These affective contributions are important in the context of science education because anxiety and low self-efficacy in the laboratory environment can negatively affect students' achievement (Bandura, 1997; Mallow, 2006). Especially in fields such as chemistry, where experimental implementations are intensive, the psychological preparation of pre-service teachers is a determining factor in success (Hofstein & Lunetta, 2004). The pre-service teachers came to the laboratory feeling ready to perform the experiment, confident in their ability to do so thanks to the simulations they had completed before the experiment. These results align with the literature, which shows that student-centered and virtual learning environment-based pre-laboratory practices positively impact not only achievement but also students' affective characteristics (Makransky, Thisgaard, & Gadegaard, 2016; Scheckler, 2003).

5. CONCLUSIONS:

In conclusion, this study demonstrates that a blended laboratory teaching model incorporating simulations alongside student-prepared flowcharts can have a positive impact on pre-service teachers' academic achievement, as well as their perspectives and readiness for the laboratory experience. Qualitative data obtained from pre-service teachers' opinions revealed that simulations contributed to the process not only at the knowledge level but also emotionally. These findings suggest that enriching laboratory practices with digital tools and student-centered activities can contribute to the learning process in multiple ways. Today, when educational technologies are increasingly integrated into learning environments, simulations can be considered as a powerful tool to ensure the active participation of pre-service teachers in experimental processes. Especially in environments where laboratory resources are limited or pre-service teachers' experimental self-confidence is low, it is recommended that such technological supports be systematically incorporated into the teaching process. Future studies may compare similar practices across disciplines or topics and evaluate their long-term effects on learning retention and transfer.

6. DECLARATIONS

6.1. Study Limitations

1. Since the participants were pre-service teachers enrolled in the General Chemistry Laboratory course, the sample was restricted to the number of students taking this course. Consequently, the relatively

small sample size limits the statistical power of the study and reduces the generalizability of the findings to broader populations.

2. The study was initially designed as a single group pretest–posttest experimental design. However, although 10 pre-service teachers initially agreed to construct a flowchart and confirmed their participation through the consent form, they later decided not to construct the flowchart during the implementation process. As a result, the design shifted into a static-group pretest–posttest experimental design.
3. The comparatively low number of participants in both experimental and control groups is a limitation in the research and presents challenges in generalizing the results to larger populations.
4. External variables that may influence pre-service teachers' academic achievement were not included in this study.

6.2. Acknowledgements

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6.3. Funding source

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6.4. Competing Interests

The authors declare no potential conflict of interest in this publication.

6.5. Open Access

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7. HUMAN AND ANIMAL-RELATED STUDIES

7.1. Ethical Approval

Ethical approval for this study was granted by the Research Ethics Committee of the Institute of Educational Sciences at Hacettepe University, Türkiye, on 08.08.2025 (Approval No: E-51944218-050-00004400126)

7.2. Informed Consent

The pre-service teachers who participated in the study filled out the consent form. We would like to thank the pre-service teachers who participated in this research on a voluntary basis.

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Table 1. Wilcoxon signed-rank test results achievement pretest-posttest scores for control group

Observed variables		Mean rank	Sum of ranks	Z	p
Achievement exam	Negative ranks	3.00	3.00	-2.312	.021*
	Positive ranks	5.25	42.00		

*p<0.05

a. Based on negative ranks.

Table 2. Wilcoxon signed-rank test results achievement pretest-posttest scores for experimental group

Observed variables		Mean rank	Sum of ranks	Z	p
Achievement exam	Negative ranks	.00	.00	-2.807	.005*
	Positive ranks	5.50	55.00		

*p<0.05

a. Based on negative ranks.

Table 3. Mann Whitney test results achievement posttest scores

Group	N	Mean rank	Sum of ranks	U	Z	p
Group A	10	7.00	70.00	15.000	-2.822	.005*
Group B	11	14.64	161.00			

*p<0.05